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Dr. P. Geetha¹**Abstract**

Developing countries like India would have to concentrate in its foreign trade and especially in its exports rather than imports to have favourable balance of trade. Taxes are levied and duties are charged by government plays vital role for improvising trade. Even though foreign trade is out of GST, this is study just focusing of impact of GST implementation in India. After the introduction of GST trade balance is decreased in every month except in the month of November and January and it shows GST has positive impact in foreign trade in India.

Keywords: Balance of Trade, GST.

1.1 Introduction

Any Business activities with an aim of making profit are trade or otherwise named as economic activities. Trade may be classified as national and foreign trade. Trade could be a key factor to economic development. Developing countries like India would have to concentrate in its foreign trade and especially in its exports rather than imports to have favourable balance of trade. Balance of trade denotes the difference between merchandise exports and merchandise imports of country. The excess of exports over imports indicates favourable balance of trade while an excess of imports over exports denotes adverse balance of trade. Taxes are levied and duties are charged by government plays vital role for improvising trade.

1.2 Review of Literature

Ram (1985)¹ examined individual country growth model for 85 less developed countries on the basis of time series data for 1960-1982. His results indicate that the role of exports in growth is predominantly positive.

Ukpolo (1994)² also used time series data for eight African countries. While his results show some positive linkages between manufactured exports and economic growth, the relationship is not significant in terms of its contribution towards economic growth.

1.3 Objectives of the study

Present study has the following objectives

- 1) To know about the exports from the year April 2012 – March 2013 to April 2017 – February 2018
- 2) To know about the imports from the year April 2012 – March 2013 to April 2017 – February 2018
- 3) To know about the balance of trade from the year April 2012 – March 2013 to April 2017 – February 2018
- 4) To know about the trend line of exports and imports of India during the study period of five years

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- 5) To identify the impact of GST on the balance of trade after the implementation of GST
- 6) To give findings based on the study.

1.4 Period of study

Study period is five accounting periods April 2012 - March 2013 to April 2016 to March 2017 and additionally GST implemented year i.e. April 2017 to February 2018 (11 months). Hence study period is 5 years and 11 months.

1.5 Research Methodology

This is analytical type of research because the researcher has used already available facts or information which is collected from the Reserve bank of India website. Even though foreign trade is out of GST, this is study just focusing of impact of GST implementation in India.

1.6 Type of data and its source

Secondary data is used for the present study and it is collected from the website of Reserve Bank of India. (www.rbi.org.in)

1.7 Tools of analysis

Amount of increase/decrease in exports, imports and trade balance for the study period. (5 years and 11 months) Percentage increase and decrease for exports, imports and trade balance for five-year period. (2012-13 to 2016-17). Straight line trend is found using formula of $Yc = a + bx$ taken x as year of study and y as amount of exports and imports.

1.8 Data analysis and interpretation

Knowing about balance of trade is essential for the present study. Hence it is collected, presented from table no 1.1 to 1.9, used for analysis and interpretation is written based on the analysis.

1.9 Trade balance from April 2017 - February 2018. (When GST introduced)

Table 1 Details of Trade Balance from April 2017 to February 2018
(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2017-18	April	1584.91	2457.24	-872.33	Nil
2017-18	May	1542.80	2443.50	-900.70	+ 28.37
2017-18	June	1483.41	2372.97	-889.56	- 11.14
2017-18	July	1434.60	2209.36	-774.76	-114.8
2017-18	August	1482.63	2306.37	-823.74	+ 48.98
2017-18	September	1828.02	2443.49	-615.47	-208.27
2017-18	October	1487.26	2437.62	-950.35	+334.88
2017-18	November	1692.08	2621.52	-929.44	- 20.91
2017-18	December	1778.03	2692.35	-914.32	- 15.12
2017-18	January	1588.12	2587.58	-999.46	+85.14
2017-18	February	1663.06	2434.20	-771.15	- 228.31

Source: rbi.org.in

From the tale no 1.1, it is evident that there was an adverse balance of trade through out in every months of the year 2017 imports are excess than exports in India. There was a lesser negative trade balance during the month of September 2017 when the GST was introduced and it was decreased up to the amount of 208.27 billion, exports amounted to Rupees 1828.02 billion. During the month of February 2018 exports are increased to Rupees 74.84 billion and imports are decreased when comparing the previous month of January 2018.

1.10 Pre-GST period

Details in table 1.2 to 1.6 are Post GST period. Hence researcher presented data about exports, imports and trade balance of India.

Table 2 Details of Trade Balance from April 2016 to March 2017
(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2016-17	April	1386.78	1707.55	-320.76	Nil
2016-17	May	1499.18	1892.54	-393.36	+72.6
2016-17	June	1524.65	2080.62	-555.97	+162.61
2016-17	July	1457.89	1969.54	-511.65	-44.32
2016-17	August	1445.70	1961.54	-515.84	+4.19
2016-17	September	1519.51	2124.86	-605.36	+89.52
2016-17	October	1559.27	2302.47	-743.20	+137.84
2016-17	November	1356.99	2262.88	-905.89	+162.69
2016-17	December	1633.44	2349.52	-716.08	-189.81
2016-17	January	1522.03	2196.35	-674.32	-41.76
2016-17	February	1658.56	2297.23	-638.67	-35.65
2016-17	March	1919.95	2613.26	-693.31	+54.64
2016-17	Annual	18540.96	25668.20	-7127.24	

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table it is evident that highest amount of import Rupees 2613.26 billion during the month of March 2017 and the highest export amount is Rupees 1919.95 billion and during the month of November 2016 smallest amount of export (Rupees 1356.99 billion) was happened from our country when the demonetization was announced and the corresponding period trade balance is increased upto the amount of Rupees 162.69 billion.

Table 3 Details of Trade Balance from April 2015 to March 2016
(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2015-16	April	1389.18	2102.64	-713.46	Nil
2015-16	May	1437.36	2095.06	-657.70	-55.76
2015-16	June	1425.61	2141.65	-716.04	+58.34
2015-16	July	1481.50	2314.54	-833.04	+117
2015-16	August	1404.43	2211.27	-806.83	-26.21

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2015-16	September	1448.14	2121.31	-673.17	-133.66
2015-16	October	1395.89	2026.45	-630.56	-42.61
2015-16	November	1293.31	1976.66	-683.35	+52.79
2015-16	December	1504.62	2270.67	-766.06	+82.71
2015-16	January	1425.68	1941.34	-515.66	-250.4
2015-16	February	1422.46	1871.01	-448.54	-67.12
2015-16	March	1535.59	1830.39	-294.80	-153.74
2015-16	Annual	17163.78	24902.98	-7739.20	

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table it is evident that maximum amount of decrease trade balance is identified during the march 2016. Total amount of import is Rupees 24902.98 and export from India is 17163.78 billion.

Table 4 Details of Trade Balance from April 2014 to March 2015

(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2014-15	April	1558.86	2160.50	-601.64	NIL
2014-15	May	1661.68	2316.39	-654.70	+53.06
2014-15	June	1548.62	2290.82	-742.20	+87.5
2014-15	July	1550.45	2406.43	-855.97	+113.77
2014-15	August	1633.53	2281.91	-648.38	-207.59
2014-15	September	1758.37	2637.99	-879.63	+231.25
2014-15	October	1589.66	2421.09	-831.43	-48.2
2014-15	November	1635.35	2636.16	-1000.81	+169.38
2014-15	December	1642.42	2217.27	-574.85	-425.96
2014-15	January	1519.26	2007.74	-488.49	-86.36
2014-15	February	1365.33	1782.05	-416.73	-71.76
2014-15	March	1500.93	2212.52	-711.59	+294.86
2014-15	Annual	18964.45	27370.87	-8406.41	

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table no 1.4, it is evident that starting from May to July 2014 trade balance is increased and again it was increased respective month September, November 2014 and March 2015.

Table 5 Details of Trade Balance from April 2013 to March 2014

(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2013-14	April	1333.54	2260.79	-927.25	NIL
2013-14	May	1371.03	2419.77	-1048.73	+121.48
2013-14	June	1401.44	2061.68	-660.24	-388.49
2013-14	July	1544.30	2290.98	-746.68	+86.44
2013-14	August	1664.79	2340.37	-675.58	-71.1
2013-14	September	1793.72	2184.03	-390.31	-285.27
2013-14	October	1693.20	2346.01	-652.81	+262.5

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2013-14	November	1515.83	2115.30	-599.47	-53.34
2013-14	December	1634.00	2264.68	-630.68	+31.21
2013-14	January	1669.32	2256.23	-586.91	-43.77
2013-14	February	1577.69	2094.95	-517.26	-69.65
2013-14	March	1851.23	2519.54	-668.31	+151.05
2013-14	Annual	19050.11	27154.34	-8104.23	

Source: rbi.org.in

It is clear from the table no 1.5 highest exports of goods from our country had done during March 2014 and the smallest amount of import is identified during the month June 2013.

Table 6 Details of Trade Balance from April 2012 to March 2013

(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Month	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance	Decrease/ Increase in Trade Balance
2012-13	April	1232.71	1977.72	-745.02	NIL
2012-13	May	1352.11	2298.09	-945.98	+200.96
2012-13	June	1396.51	2025.90	-629.39	-316.59
2012-13	July	1281.92	2254.17	-972.24	+342.85
2012-13	August	1285.35	2072.78	-787.44	-184.8
2012-13	September	1359.79	2296.24	-936.45	+149.01
2012-13	October	1274.32	2345.98	-1071.66	+135.21
2012-13	November	1273.59	2215.90	-942.31	-129.35
2012-13	December	1391.20	2352.62	-961.42	+19.11
2012-13	January	1400.03	2430.93	-1030.91	+69.49
2012-13	February	1434.08	2193.54	-759.46	-271.45
2012-13	March	1661.59	2227.75	-566.15	-193.31
2012-13	Annual	16343.18	26691.62	-10348.44	

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table no 1.6 it is evident that trade balance is more during the month of October 2012 (Rupees 1071.66 billion)

1.11 Annual amount of Trade Balance

Details of exports, imports and trade balance for five-year periods are presented in table no 1.7 and chart no 1.1

Table 7 Details of Exports, Imports and Trade Balance from 2012-13 to 2016-17

(Rupees in Billion)

Year	Exports	Imports	Trade Balance
2012-13	16343.18	26691.62	-10348.44
2013-14	19050.11	27154.34	-8104.23
2014-15	18964.45	27370.87	-8406.41
2015-16	17163.78	24902.98	-7739.20
2016-17	18540.96	25668.2	-7127.24

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table no 1.7, it is clear that trade balance is decreased year after year from 2012 -13 to 2016 -17 for the five years period. Least amount of trade balance is experienced during the year 2016 -2017. In case of exports there was a fluctuation during the study period. In the case of imports, it was increased during 2013 -14, 2014 -15 and 2016 -17.

1.12 Percentage increase/ decrease in Trade Balance
In table no 1.8 percentage increase or decrease in exports, imports and trade balance for five years period of study is calculated for each item and is given below

Table 8 Exports, Imports and Trade Balance from 2012-13 to 2016-17
(Rupees in Billion)

Sl. No.	Year	Exports	Percentage increase/ decrease	Imports	Percentage increase/ decrease	Trade Balance	Percentage increase/ decrease
1	2012-13	16343.18		26691.62		-10348.44	
2	2013-14	19050.11	16.56	27154.34	1.73	-8104.23	-20.92
3	2014-15	18964.45	-0.44	27370.87	0.78	-8406.41	3.73
4	2015-16	17163.78	-9.50	24902.98	-9.02	-7739.20	-7.94
5	2016-17	18540.96	8.02	25668.2	3.07	-7127.24	-7.91

Source: rbi.org.in

From table no 1.8 it is evident that highest increase of exports is done during the year 2016 -17 and an import is done during the year 2014 -15. Trade balance is decreased in all the study period except during the year 2014-15.

1.13 Trend line of Exports and Imports

In table 9 and 10 exports, imports and its trend are presented.

Table 9 Details of Exports and its trend line

year	exports	Trend (Yc)
2012-13	16343.18	17510.65
2013-14	19050.11	17761.573
2014-15	18964.45	18012.496
2015-16	17163.78	18263.419
2016-17	18540.96	18514.342

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table no 1.9 it is clear that government of India taking steps to improve the export of goods because the straight-line trend is upwardly moving and it is clearly noticed in the below chart no 1.2.

Table 10 Details of Imports and its trend line

Year	Imports	Trend (Yc)
2012-13	26691.62	27217.242
2013-14	27154.34	26787.422
2014-15	27370.87	26357.602
2015-16	24902.98	25927.782
2016-17	25668.2	25497.962

Source: rbi.org.in

From the table no 10 it is clear that trend line of imports is moving downward and its clearly noticed from the chart no 1.3. It shows imports amount is decreased year after year and our country is concentrating reduction of import of goods and our Indian economy will definitely change from its present level as emerging economy to developed economy.

1.14 Findings of the study

From the study it is found that highest increase of exports is done during the year 2016 -17 and an import is done during the year 2014 -15. It is also evident that there was an adverse balance of trade throughout the study period year though imports are excess than exports in India and undoubtedly Trade balance is decreased in all the study period except during the year 2014-15. Government of India taking steps to improve the export of goods because the straight-line trend is upwardly moving and trend line of imports is moving downward and it is clearly noticed from the chart no 1.3. It shows imports amount is decreased year after year and our country is concentrating reduction of import of goods and our Indian economy will definitely change from its present level as emerging economy to developed economy. There was a lesser negative trade balance during the month of September 2017 when the GST was introduced and it was decreased up to the amount of 208.27 billion, exports amounted to Rupees 1828.02 billion. After the introduction of GST trade balance is decreased in every month except in the month of November and January and it shows GST has positive impact in foreign trade in India.

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